

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS OF THE APPLICATION PLATFORM OF DIGITAL ADMINISTRATION WITH TRANSFORMATIONAL CHANGES IN THE OPERATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

The article proposes a conceptual approach to substantiating the management technology of construction enterprises as an innovative unifier, formed on the basis of determining the level of their management and technological maturity, which will allow to ensure a dynamic level of development within the traditional formats of economic interests of enterprises. A methodology has been developed for the formation of a mechanism for the introduction of a complex of innovative technologies into the management activities of construction enterprises, which makes it possible on the basis of hierarchical incorporation (classical diagnosis and zoning of the enterprise, determination of the level of managerial and technological maturity; determination of the genetic predisposition of the enterprise to a certain level of acceptance of the project of change management; formation of a pool of attractors for the transition to a new level of management of operational activities; to form such a horizon of events that will allow the enterprise to move in the direction of development determined by the attractor. The methodological approaches of forming the genotype of innovative management technology at enterprises, the construction industry consisting of two structural levels (the level of professional and cognitive competence and the level of information and communication potential). This allows for a transformational transition of the genotype of management technology to an innovative state for management optimization which activities of the enterprises-sakeholders of construction.

Keywords: business process, management systems, process approach to modeling, technology modeling business processes, transformational changes, the operational activities.

At the present time, the philosophy of economics explores deep turning transformations that are taking place both in economic relations and in economic theory, to which it is appropriate to attribute three main aspects: globalization, information dominance and the new economy of knowledge. The Internet, as the most vivid manifestation of new information technologies, has today become a symbol of the new world, new political and economic decisions, and modern man. That is, the economy based on knowledge under the influence of globalization processes and new computer technologies, which include the Internet, has turned into a new economy - digital. Thus, the digital economy is a symbiosis of three economies: financial, global and informational.

Today, the key category of economic growth is innovations, the most important feature of which is the novelty of their consumer properties. Therefore, innovations are accompanied by radical and often permanent transformations, which are based on modern achievements in the field of science, technology and technology, which quite often requires special knowledge, skills and creative energy in the field of their development and practical application, as well as the appropriate material and technical base, adequate management system.

It is the level of innovativeness of management technologies that is a modern indicator of determining the level of managerial and technological maturity and the functional capabilities of developing the business

prospects of an enterprise in the conditions of a dynamic environment for the long term, since the main feature of the modern development of economic systems is the process of constant transformation as an environment in which integration processes change market space, turning it into an integrative landscape of a new development format, as well as an internal environment in which constant changes in operating conditions cause continuous movement, creating additional opportunities and threats. An imperative feature of such a model is innovativeness as a cross-functional generator of the formation of new vectors of development and optimal sources of dynamic changes. It is the movement of open complex socio-economic systems, to which the enterprise undoubtedly belongs, that is the basis of the formation of a new economic model of the construction economy in the context of the geo-economic development strategy.

Scientific achievements of the last decade prove the possibility of managing certain extremely complex processes with the help of such management systems, in which management tools, methods and models create an economic-technological continuum of coherent management technologies. The qualitative impact on the enterprise management system largely depends on the level of development of technologies used in the enterprise.

With due respect to recognized scientists and their works, it is worth noting that various aspects of the operation and development of the enterprise were studied from the standpoint of enterprise security, sustainable

development, anti-crisis management, synergistic and adaptive approaches to the management of the economic, production, and social system of the enterprise, but the issues in the context of innovative enterprise management technologies in the conditions of a dynamic business environment has not been sufficiently studied, as well as the fully functional structuring of methods and opportunities for subtle and gradual adjustment of enterprise development with the help of management technologies.

The purpose of the research is the scientific substantiation of the theoretical and development of methodological provisions and organizational and practical recommendations for the formation of a complex of innovative technologies in the management of enterprises in the conditions of a dynamic business environment.

Achieving the specified goal made it necessary to perform the following tasks:

- to investigate the genesis and modern concepts of the formation of management activities of enterprises;
- summarize the factors of the business environment that shape the choice of technologies in the management activities of enterprises and justify the conceptual approach of innovativeness of their management activities;
- to substantiate the formation of innovative management technologies of enterprises in the construction industry in the conditions of a dynamic business environment;
- generalize the imperatives of forming innovative technologies of modern management of enterprises in the construction industry;
- form the concept of introducing innovative technologies into the management activities of enterprises based on the theory of innovative dynamics;
- to improve the theoretical and methodological basis for the selection of innovative technologies in the management activities of the enterprise;
- formalize the parametric criteria for the introduction of innovative management technologies into the activities of enterprises;
- to propose a methodological approach to determine the state of equilibrium of the enterprise in the conditions of a dynamic business environment;
- propose a methodological approach to the formation of a mechanism for introducing a complex of innovative technologies into the management activities of enterprises;
- to justify the system-wide determinants of the dynamic development of the business environment of the construction industry and to carry out structural and functional modeling of the application of innovative technologies in the management of enterprises in the construction industry;
- carry out a diagnosis of the level of managerial and technological maturity and form a complex of innovative management technologies of enterprises in the construction industry;
- to form a descriptive model of optimization of a complex of innovative management technologies in a dynamic environment;

- justify the genotype of innovative management technology for enterprises in the construction industry;

- forecast the development of enterprises in the construction industry and propose optimization of the complex of innovative management technologies.

The modern innovative technology for modeling business processes should be based on the concept of process-oriented accounting of enterprise expenses. It is closely connected with such management concepts as total quality management (TQM), enterprise resource planning (ERP), workflow management system (WFM).

To apply the process approach at the enterprise using the principles of the ISO 9000:2000 standard, the organization needs:

- identify the processes necessary for the quality management system, and their applications within the organization;
- determine the sequence of these processes and their relationship;
- determine the criteria and methods necessary to ensure confidence that both these processes themselves and their management are effective;
- provide confidence in the availability of resources and information necessary to support the implementation of these processes and their monitoring;
- observe, measure and analyze these processes;

Implement the measures necessary to achieve the planned results and continuous improvement of these processes.

In recent years, the approach to process automation has changed. If the task of traditional systems of process automation was to simulate the business processes of the enterprise, then the task of modern, currently required systems is the direct execution of business processes in a computer environment. In the development and implementation of such systems, there are some problems associated with the automation of the enterprise management process. Traditional approaches of the theory of process approach which solutions do not give. The new process approach is proposed that allows excluding routine operations from the actions of employees, increasing the speed of employee interaction, effectively optimizing existing business processes, and quickly rebuilding the enterprise's business processes in response to significant changes in business conditions.

The qualitative changes are taking place in the automation of the process management of modern enterprises in recent years. New software products have appeared on the market designed to automate modern enterprises at a fairly high level. It has been found that the development of scientific methodology, methods and tools of enterprise management and modern economic challenges necessitated the creation of new scientific directions and concepts for the formation of managerial activities, the introduction and use of new tools, methods and approaches to ensure opportunities for enterprise development in a dynamic business environment. Innovative enterprise management technology acts as a materialized result of the implementation of a newly

created or improved algorithm of actions aimed at optimal and adaptive improvement of individual types of enterprise activities to create a coherent mechanism for managing the dynamic development of enterprises. It has been proven that in the theory of modern management, it is possible to single out a number of basic management technologies, which represent a set of methods and mechanisms of influence, thanks to which the possibilities of dynamic development of the enterprise are realized.

The development of the modern economy is determined by the high pace of economic and technological transformations, which is intensified by competition in industries and dynamic changes in the needs of the audience. However, the domestic business sphere shows signs of prolonged stagnation, overcoming which is a critically important task for the development of the Ukrainian economy at both the macro and micro levels. Therefore, the choice of innovation as the driving force

of progress simultaneously encourages positive shifts not only in scientific thought, but also qualitative changes in the entire system.

According to the liberal concept of the economy, there are special conditions for the activity of business entities, which are based on the processes of the macroeconomic situation with the provision of appropriate institutional changes and relate to freedom of choice, price policy, collaborative processes and information flows. At the same time, business, as a system as a whole, affects all the constituent structures of the organization, which violates their independence, affects the dynamics of development, inhibiting the progress of changes both at the level of the country and each organization separately. This especially applies to innovative business development in the context of digital transformations, which is a new dimension of reality with the definition of digital leadership.

Table 1.

Classification of operational processes

Process parameters	Planning	Execution	Control	Completion
Integration	Project Management planning development	Direction and management of the project implementation	Monitoring and management of the project; General change management.	Project close
Contents	Content planning; Definition of content.	–	Confirmation of content; Content management	–
Terms	Determining the composition of operations; Defining relationships operations; Estimated resource operations	Estimation of the duration of operations; Network Design	Schedule management	–
Cost	Valuation. Cost Budget Development	–	Cost management	–
Quality	Quality planning	Quality assurance process	Quality control process	–
Staff	Human resource planning	Recruitment of the project team; Project team development	Project team management	–
Communications	Communication planning	Spread of information	Performance reporting; Project participant management	–
Risks	Risk management planning; Qualitative risk analysis; Risk Response Planning.	Risk identification	Monitoring and risk management	–
Contracts	Planning for purchases and acquisitions; Contract planning	Request information from sellers. Sellers Choice	Contract administration	Contract close

Digital technologies in the modern world create fundamentally new opportunities for building interaction between the state, business and the population, eliminating long chains of intermediaries and speeding up various deals and operations. Such factors come to the fore due to the rapid development of information

technologies and the globalization of the economy, which offer fundamentally new concepts of consumption and open up additional potential for the development of new markets and innovative developments.

A new ideology of the process of innovation is proposed as a prognostic idea of business development

in the conditions of the digital economy at the macro and micro levels, based on the construction of a knowledge society taking into account the laws, values, processes of integration in the conditions of the globalization of the information and technological space and the transformation of business models, information and communication paradigm with the use of digitization methods, new approaches to the formation of intellectual capital and innovative culture in organizations,

which makes it possible to ensure an integral effect during the transformation of modern world socio-economic processes.

The membership functions for three indicators that characterize the structure of the enterprise and can be described by terms such as "enough to ensure transformational and adaptive capabilities of enterprises" are systematized in the table. 2 and a system of fuzzy logical inference rules is given.

Table 2

Membership functions of all indicators for the terms "level necessary to ensure change management"

Indicator	Membership function
T₁ – type of organizational structure	$\mu(T_1) = \begin{cases} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{T_1 - 1}{0,4247} \right)^2}, & T_1 < 0,4247 \\ 1, & T_1 \geq 0,4247 \end{cases}$
T₂ – the effectiveness of communications between management personnel and employees of lower levels of management	$\mu(T_2) = \begin{cases} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{T_2 - 0,112}{0,6317} \right)^2}, & T_2 < 0,6317 \\ 1, & T_2 \geq 0,6317 \end{cases}$
T₃ – degree of digitization of business processes	$\mu(T_3) = \begin{cases} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{T_3 - 0,5188}{0,99} \right)^2}, & T_3 < 0,99 \\ e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{T_3 + 0,272}{0,097} \right)^2}, & T_3 > 0,097 \\ 0, & T_3 \geq 0,99 \\ 0, & T_3 \leq 0,097 \end{cases}$

The first advantage of the process approach allows increasing management efficiency by reorganizing the business processes of the enterprise in response to significant changes in business conditions, as well as by optimizing existing business processes in stable periods.

The second advantage of the process approach allows excluding routine operations, ineffective procedures associated with the search and transmission of information from the actions of employees, significantly increasing the speed of employee interaction. This advantage allows significantly increase the productivity of workers.

The third advantage of the process approach allows using modern means of process automation to solve the problem of integrating heterogeneous enterprise systems into a single corporate information system.

The recent innovative technology automates the process management of enterprises. This is a special class of computer systems has appeared which is called business process management systems (BPMS). The main task of such systems is to distribute tasks to performers and monitor their implementation. The sequence of tasks is determined by the business process diagram, which can be developed and further quickly modified using the business process editor. This diagram is similar to a block diagram of an algorithm. The scheme moves the control points. In circuit nodes tasks for performers are generated.

The modern BPMS should be provides the following areas:

- Development of business processes in a graphical environment.
- Execution of instances of business processes.
- Monitoring the status of business processes.
- Maintaining a history of business process events.
- Grading applications using connectors to external systems used by business processes.
- User administration.
- It is necessary to consider main advantages in more detail.

On the basis of a comprehensive approach to the process of creating innovative management technology, five basic imperatives of the innovative transformation process are identified: the global threshold of knowledge; the amount of financial resources for innovation; the presence of an innovative personnel component; field of innovative activity; innovative climate.

The generalized structure of the technology is based on three groups of quantitative and qualitative parameters, which are filters for the definition of the technology: the basic essence of the technology (a set of system and applied methodology, principles and mechanisms that are used within the framework of the technology to implement its essential characteristics), specific functionality (a set of tools and potentials that are possible to achieve optimal results at this enterprise) and the necessary knowledge base for the implementa-

tion of the technology (a set of structured data reflecting the state of the object, its properties and characteristics, relationships organized for storage, structuring, analysis and information retrieval). Depending on the identified system features, a synthetic model of the

transformation of traditional management technologies into innovative management technologies is proposed.

A system of fuzzy logic inference was created using the Matlab Fuzzy Logic Toolbox package of application programs with the help of a Madame type fuzzy inference system (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. A system of fuzzy inference rules

The connection of business process nodes with task performers is established using roles. This role is created and mapped to certain nodes of the scheme in the development of a business process. It is necessary to determine the executors for the roles during the execution of the business process instance in the BPMS.

Initialization of a role is an assignment to a role of a specific executor. There is a problem of choice specific executives to whom the task will be sent during the transition from modeling business processes on a computer to the execution of business processes in a computer environment.

To solve this problem, in many BPMS, a hierarchical organizational structure of the enterprise is defined and roles are initialized by specifying the parameters of this structure. Sometimes the role initialization procedure is carried out from BPMS to some other enterprise information system. In this case, a reference to the remote function of this system is placed in the business process and the mechanism for calling the remote function is configured.

Both of these approaches have disadvantages. Setting up a remote function call from another information system is usually technically difficult. Defining the hierarchical organizational structure of an enterprise within an BPMS also does not always help. Using this structure, it is easy to initialize roles that correspond to the hierarchy of administrative management, but it is difficult to initialize roles that are not directly related to administrative management.

The success of business development in the conditions of digital transformation requires a clear understanding of the basic principles and mechanisms inherent in the digital economy. It is suggested that the methodological principles of the digital economy include the principles due to the systemic approach to the defined guiding ideas, namely: spatial, economic, technological, informational, intellectual, social, innovative, virtual, and trust and security. The systematicity of the recommended principles of the digital economy is of great importance, as it affects the understanding of its methodology, contributes to the solution of tasks, the determination of ways of its construction on both the macro and micro levels.

In the broadest sense, under the process "digitalization" means socio-economic transformation initiated by the mass introduction and assimilation of digital technologies. Offered "digitalization" should be classified as one of the main methods of the digital economy, with an emphasis on the fact that the digitalization of the economy and society is one of the most important challenges of modern times, which radically changes the established business processes and opens up a whole range of opportunities for business transformation.

References

1. M. Arthur, V. Lindsay. Knowledgeatwork : creativecollaborationintheglobaleconomy. Boston: BlackwellPublishing, 2006. 297 p.

2. H. Elbardan, A. Othman, R. Kholeif. *Enterprise Resource Planning, Corporate Governance and Internal Auditing. An Institutional Perspective*, Cham

3. S. Kortmann. The Relationship between Organizational Structure and Organizational Ambidexterity. A Comparison between Manufacturing and Service Firm, Springer Gabler, 2012. 183 p. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-8349-3630-1>

4. T. Marchuk, D Ryzhakov, G. Ryzhakova, S. Stetsenko. Identification of the basic elements of the innovation-analytical platform for energy efficiency in project financing, *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, Volume 14, Issue 4, 2017, pp. 12-20, [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi.14\(4\).2017.02](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi.14(4).2017.02)

5. Miller R., Strombom D., Iammarino M., Black B. The commercial real estate revolution: nine transforming keys to lowering costs, cutting waste, and driving change in a broken industry, *John Wiley & Sons*, 2009. 352 p.

V. Mihaylenko, T. Honcharenko, K. Chupryna, Yu. Andrashko, S. Budnik. Modeling of Spatial Data on the Construction Site Based on Multidimensional Information Objects in '*International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT)*', ISSN: 2249-8958 (Online), Volume-8 Issue-6, August 2019, Page No. 3934-3940. URL: <https://www.ijeat.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/v8i6/F9057088619.pdf>

ОХРАНА ТРУДА НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ ЭЛЕКТРОТЕХНИЧЕСКОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ

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Аннотация

Охрана труда является неотъемлемой частью любого промышленного предприятия, поскольку обеспечивает безопасную деятельность работников и тем самым минимизируя травматизм на производстве. Служба охраны труда промышленного предприятия путем выполнения достаточно широкого спектра задач, создает наиболее благоприятные условия труда работников значительно повышая их уровень безопасности.

Abstract

Occupational safety is an integral part of any industrial enterprise, as it ensures the safe activity of workers and thereby minimizes injuries at work. The labor protection service of an industrial enterprise, by performing a wide range of tasks, creates the most favorable working conditions for workers, significantly increasing their level of safety.